

THEORETICAL BACKGROUNDS RELATED TO FOREIGN WORDS

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Annotation: *The article investigates theoretical foundations of foreign words and some theoretical opinions by linguists. Along the article it will be answered what is the main factor of vocabulary enriching and the role of foreign words in a particular language.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada xorijiy so'zlarning dastlabki nazariyalari va bir ancha tilshunoslarning ilmiy fikrlari yoritiladi. Maqola davomida ma'lum bir tilning so'zlar bilan boyishining asosiy faktori nima ekanligiga javob beriladi. Hamda xorijiy so'zlarning tildagi o'rni haqida gapiriladi.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *xorijiy so'zlar, adabiy so'zlar, 'donor' til leksikologiyasi, neologizmlar*

Any natural language is constantly evolving, one of common ways of replenishing vocabulary is borrowing from external languages. Entering the language system, foreign words, neologisms-borrowings are adapted in the new language environment time by time.

Vocabulary of any language is in the process of changing and providing new words from other languages. There are some theoretical concepts by world linguists on supplementing lexical unit of a language. According to N.N.Amosova, to provide one of the most important language functions, and it is communicative, the vocabulary undergoes changes, occurring in various spheres of life and activity of people who some speak a certain language.

At B.E. Zernov has his own point of view. He believes that the emergence of new words in the language is necessary, natural process brought to life by the very essence of language as a social product and essential means of human communication.

According to I.V. Arnold, the lexicon system is always in a process of fluctuating. And also it belongs to communication and cultural exchanging between different nations so far.

No language is isolated and static or stable. Language is just like a river flowing every moment, modifying itself, improving itself, wearing the marks of time and events touching it.

In modern Russian linguistics there is no unity in interpretation, basic concepts that relate to the movement of language elements from one language system to another. Therefore, under borrowing the influence of another language is generally understood (O. S. Akhmanova), and the impact of limited vocabulary - dialects, jargons - into the literary language (S. O. Kartsevsky, L. P. Krysin), as well as the process moving different language elements from one language to another. The Russian linguists investigated the next terms for the phenomenon studied in their philological works: such as: "Foreign words", "lexical borrowings", "borrowed word", "borrowing", "foreign language element", "foreign borrowings".

Those who primarily utilize new words probably use them at first stage only with speakers of the source language who understand the actual meaning of the word. However those who do not understand the new word meaning, the word may sound 'foreign'. At this stage, when most speakers do not know the word and if they hear it think it is from another language, the word can be called a foreign word. There are many foreign words and phrases used in English such as *bon vivant* from French language, *mutatis mutandis* from Latin language, and *Fahrvergnuegen* from German language.

Also linguists differentiated literary vocabulary into many groups. According to their investigation, the literary vocabulary consists of the following groups of words: 1. common literary; 2. terms and learned words; 3. poetic words; 4. archaic words; 5. barbarisms and foreign words; 6. literary coinages including nonce-words. As it seen above, foreign words are the part of literary vocabulary. These foreign words in the English vocabulary are helping to complete a terminological function of linguistics. They still keep their foreign appearance. For instance, *ukase*, *udarnik*, *soviet*, *kolkhoz* and the like denote certain concepts which reflect an objective reality unfamiliar to English-speaking communities.

"Some people say you can never truly understand a word from another culture, but I don't think that's true," says Tim Lomas, author of *The Happiness Dictionary*. "You might not get all its layers, but there might be new layers formed, based on your own cultural understanding."

Tim Lomas wanted to say that a word is an inner part of particular language, in order to understand this or that word, users should have knowledge about foreign cultures and traditions.

Gaining something new from another culture and also cross cultures' foreign words are the idea behind books like *The Little Book of Hygge*, by Meik Wiking, *Lagom: The Swedish Art of Balanced Living*, by Linnea Dunne, and *Bella Figura: How to Live, Love, and Eat the Italian Way*, by Kamin Mohammadi. The latest entry to these volumes is *Niksen: Embracing the Dutch Art of Doing Nothing*, by Olga Mecking, who noted in her viral New York Times article about nixen that it "shows you have to take a break from all the busyness while giving you sincere, heartfelt permission to do nothing."

In the book named '*Gobbledegook. Foreignisms in English. Абракадабра*' by Larisa Sshitova, One remarkable example is given below for foreign phrase:

Cherchez la femme- searching for a woman. Definition: Look for the woman: said humorously to suggest that a woman maybe the cause of a problem or puzzle; suggests that a woman is likely to be the root cause of the problem or crime. The language of origin is French. Sentence example: *in this type of crime, my first instinct is always cherchez la femme.*

However, in time more speakers can become familiar with a new foreign word or expression. The community of users of this word can grow to the point where even people who know little or nothing of the source language understand, and even use, the novel word themselves. The new word becomes conventionalized: part of the conventional ways of speaking in the borrowing language. At this point we call it a borrowing or loanword.

English is more than any other language borrowing words from foreign languages and can be described as an "insatiable borrower", as Crystal remarked.

The upcoming theory run by Yu.S.Sarokin and V.M. Aristova, they explained the process of adoption new word, as mentioned above, words are perhaps conventionalized, according to their viewpoint, for example the process of borrowing most often means only lexical borrowing. In general, linguists consider assimilation of a foreign word in the receiving language, i.e. under borrowing is understood not only as transferred, but also completely the word mastered by the borrowing language.

As stated by L.L.Nelyubin, word borrowing is observing donor language lexicology in order to produce new concepts in other languages.

Also there are some viewpoints by Russian linguist A.V.Kalinina, she remarked that borrowing is the most suitable word for the words that have already joined in dictionary of language, otherwise the term foreign and external words are utterly alien and they are not included into the language vocabulary. It denotes foreign words are absolutely alien words and have not been joined English dictionary. However the term borrowing is another thing she said. Because borrowed words still exist in dictionaries of non-origin languages.

Besides, they investigated the connection of culture and lexicology in translation studies of this process, for example foreign terms in stylistic, system-descriptive, cognitive, linguoculturological, regional studies, predictive. In the 19th century attention was drawn to the stylistic and cultural aspects. A. S. Shishkov and V. I. Dal acted as opponents of borrowings, argued their "uselessness" for language. Over time came the understanding of inevitability this phenomenon in any language, and borrowings began to be studied as system-linguistic phenomenon in terms of choosing a donor language, in terms of the assimilation of the word in the recipient language (phonetic, grammatical, semantic adaptation), much attention was paid to reasons for borrowings, the place of borrowings in neology.

A.A. Reformatzkiy, remarked his next theory, foreign words are suitable to express for coloristic descriptions for example alien realities, customs, traditions, these are usually personal names, clothes, food and drinks, treatments and positions, generally he wanted to say that foreign words have no place in target language dictionaries, they are important to describe other cultures spheres. Besides them, he added 'Such untapped new foreign words look like inlays which are even written in their own letters, somehow does not conveniently...'

A.Nida was the famous translation theorist, has remarked on the book 'Language, culture and translation', the text cannot be understood without careful consideration of the language and cultural background. It indicates that every single foreign word has its cultural background, in order to produce a remarkable translation as a consequence of translating efforts, translator should have knowledge of cross cultures and traditions.

Besides there are massive linguists and philologists who investigated word adoption, such as A.P.Mayorov, Y.V.Marinova, O.V.Milovanova, O.Y.Rudenko, U.Vaynrakh, E.Khaugen, V.T.Klokov, J.Bagana, A.M.Molodkin, L.P.Krisin and others from different countries.

In my time L.P. Krysin marked the next opinion of the most important issues: the scope and content of the concept "borrowing"; reasons for borrowing; kinds broadcast units; assimilation of lexemes into native language, signs of adaptation.

Under foreign language vocabulary, following L.P. Krysin understands "every single words and expressions that came from another language, regardless of the degree of their basic in the recipient language". He added, foreign word - a word of foreign origin, used by native speakers of the receiving language, but not yet fixed in it as an integral element of the lexico-semantic system.

REFERENCES:

1. Амосова Н.Н. Этимологические основы словарного состава со-временного английского языка. М.: Изд-во лит-ры на иноязыках, 1956.
2. Carroll J. The Study of Language. Cambridge: Harvard Univ. Press, 1953
3. Jespersen O. Growth and Structure of the English Language. Oxford, 1945.
4. Serjeantson M.S. A History of Foreign Words in English. L., 1935.
5. Jespersen O. A Modern English Grammar on Historical Principles. Heidelberg, 1914. P. VI.